

eNetEditor: Rapid prototyping urban traffic scenarios for SUMO and evaluating their energy consumption

Tamás Kurczveil, Pablo Álvarez López;

*Institut für Verkehrssicherheit und Automatisierungstechnik, Technische Universität Braunschweig,
Hermann-Blenk-Straße 42, 38108 Braunschweig, Germany*

kurczveil@iva.ing.tu-bs.de, p.alvarez-lopez@tu-braunschweig.de

Abstract

The increasing mobility and transport demand and the sinking global supply of fossil energy carriers will eventually cause a growing trend towards alternative drive concepts and the development of corresponding energy supply infrastructures. These emerging solutions and their interaction with the prevailing traffic will need to be evaluated for their optimal integration. SUMO is a preferred tool when it comes to evaluating measures in urban traffic behavior. When using SUMO, however, the creation of corresponding scenarios is accompanied by challenges in network creation and corrections as well as traffic demand generation and calibration. Motivated by the projects *emil* and *InduktivLaden*, both funded by the German Federal Ministry of Transport and digital Infrastructure, this paper presents the newly developed tool eNetEditor, which allows users the rapid prototyping of custom and calibrated traffic scenarios based on traffic counts and their evaluation in regard of energy consumption.

Keywords: network generation, traffic assignment and calibration, energy consumption

1 Introduction

Current traffic is mostly driven by fossil fuels. In 2014, the number of newly registered vehicles in Germany was 3.048.507 [1]. 8522 of these vehicles (2.8 ‰) were electric vehicles [2]. The same statistic indicates that the number of electric vehicles is expected to rise in the coming years. An exponential extrapolation of these numbers yields an approximate range of 14283 to 27041 newly registered electric vehicles for the year 2015.

One of the current challenges for the customers of electric vehicles is the multiplicity of charging systems and interfaces. Whereas 14622 gas stations in Germany supply conventional traffic with the adequate amount of fossil fuel [3], only 5050 publicly available electric charging points have been installed for electric vehicles in Germany until June 2014 [4]. Many manufacturers offer proprietary solutions, tying customers to a limited amount of available charging stations, such as Tesla. In other cases, countries or regions have agreed on and effected the installation of a more consistent charging infrastructure, such as CHAdeMO in Japan and France or CCS in Germany. This heterogeneous situation has resulted in charging station infrastructures of several different manufacturers and providers with varying and largely incompatible standards. In addition to this heterogeneous situation with the charging infrastructure, new developments indicate that battery-driven electric vehicles might not remain the only alternative solution for the coming years: Most of the leading automobile manufacturers have invested many efforts into the development of hydrogen fuel-cell vehicles over the past years. Toyota, for example, has introduced one of the first of these vehicles to be sold commercially starting in 2015. This further results in a comparably increasing diversity regarding drive train concepts.

However, even with these trends, the development of new compatible charging infrastructures is still at its beginning. This situation is a chance for the introduction of more homogeneity in the charging infrastructure and, as opposed to the location of current gas stations, its optimal operational integration into prevailing traffic situations. For this unification of the energy supply infrastructure, traffic planners will need tools in the future that take into account the energy consumption of vehicles along their routes allowing the optimal positioning of components for the corresponding energy supply infrastructure. These results can further be used for infrastructure operators to determine the amount of energy that electric vehicles are expected to gain at specific locations within the road network and how much power will be required for their sufficient supply.

This paper introduces eNetEditor: a tool with a graphical user interface for traffic planners that allows the rapid prototyping of arbitrary road traffic networks and calibrated scenarios based on flow measurements and the evaluation of the corresponding energy consumption.

2 Concept

For the simulation of vehicles within the road network and their interaction with infrastructure objects and other vehicles, the microscopic traffic simulation tool SUMO (Simulation of Urban Mobility) is used [5]. SUMO is "an open source, highly portable, microscopic and continuous road traffic simulation package designed to handle large road networks" [5]. The development of SUMO was initiated by the Institute of Transportation Systems of the German Aerospace Center (DLR), in 2001. It has evolved into a traffic simulation tool, high in features, functionality and interfaces. Even though instantiated vehicles follow a simplified behavior, traffic simulation tools like SUMO allow the realistic replication of prevailing traffic in arbitrary road networks.

Implementations were presented in [6] that newly introduced a simplified energy consumption model for vehicle objects and a corresponding declared charging station class as integral parts

into SUMO. These implementations build the functional basis for the evaluation of the energy consumptions in traffic scenarios.

The application of these implementations subsequently require a traffic scenario consisting of a road network and traffic demand. Whereas a common procedure is to use open data to map transportation networks, this process is often accompanied by corrections that, if irregularities are found, are hard to carry out without the proper tools. In order to instantiate calibrated traffic in arbitrary road networks, eNetEditor (initially, a MATLAB-based tool) has been developed with a graphical user interface that allows the rapid and efficient generation of road networks. Network object data were structured such that they contain the properties required by SUMO's network generator netconvert.exe (i.e. edges, lanes, nodes, connections), by SUMO itself (e.g. vehicle types, bus stops), and arbitrary custom parameters and their values (e.g. traffic counts or other traffic demand data) for user-defined functions. The data structure for the network creation is outlined in section 3.1. After the definition of vehicles, traffic can be instantiated and calibrated from within this tool as described later in sections 3.2 and 3.3, respectively.

Using traffic data and measurements from different sources, such as flows from induction loops, eNetEditor allows the generation of traffic demand. The goal is a simulation output in form of a structure that can be used to represent energy consumption of individual vehicles over time and vehicle position or along individual lanes of a road network over time. An example urban traffic scenario will be shown in chapter 4 that was generated by eNetEditor, accompanied by evaluations in regard of its constituents' energy consumptions.

3 Implementation

This chapter explains the structure of eNetEditor's implementations. The modules are split into three parts:

1. network definition and generation,
2. vehicle definitions and generation, and
3. traffic demand generation and calibration.

The following sections in this chapter give an overview on the implementation of each of the

Figure 1: Constituents of a traffic scenario's network represented in form of a UML class daigram

modules and the used data structures that broadly represent SUMO's object structures.

3.1 Network definition and generation

A SUMO Network consists of edges, nodes, lanes, vehicle class restrictions on specified lanes, lane connections (and prohibitions), bus stops, and light signal systems. As a new infrastructure element, charging stations have been introduced. Figure 1 shows the structure of these constituents as definable in eNetEditor, axiomatizing the terms in form of a class diagram as introduced in [7] and [8]. The following sections will describe the data structure for each network constituent that can be represented in eNetEditor, the interface for their generation, and exemplified output data. Newly introduced classes and attributes are shown in green.

3.1.1 Nodes and edges

Nodes and edges constitute the essential components of a network's graph. These can be created directly in the GUI with a mouse click or by connecting two nodes with a click-and-drag. To allow efficient analyses and operations with the resulting multi-edged directed graph and its adjacency matrix, edges and their properties are stored in the 3-dimensional array E of the following structure

$$E^{n \times n \times (2m+1)} = (e_{i,j,k}), \text{ with ...} \quad (1)$$

origin node index $i = 1 \dots n,$
 destination node index $j = 1 \dots n,$
 property index $k = 1 \dots 2m+1,$
 number of nodes n and
 number of edge properties $m.$

The entries $(e_{i,j,k=1})$ represent the network graph's adjacency matrix, where each element $e_{i,j,k=1}$ equals the number of lanes from node i to node j . Edge property and corresponding value pairs are stored in successive entries of $E_{i,j,k=2,4,6,\dots}$ (property name) and $E_{i,j,k=3,5,7,\dots}$ (property value) in form of strings. Whereas SUMO and its netconvert application will only process the values of specified property tags, eNetEditor allows the declaration of arbitrary properties and property values that can be used for eNetEditor-/MATLAB-based pre-/post-processing.

Nodes and their properties are stored in the 2-dimensional array O with the following structure

$$O^{n \times 18} = (o_{i,k}), \text{ with ...} \quad (2)$$

node index $i = 1 \dots n,$
 property index $k = 1 \dots 18$ and
 number of nodes $n.$

Next to mandatory property values in $o_{i=1\dots n, j=1\dots 6}$, the remaining entries in O ($o_{i=1\dots n, j=7\dots 18}$) can be used for the declaration of arbitrary node properties and their corresponding values. The structure of the edge and node variables E and O is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 2: eNetEditor's graphical user interface
© OpenStreetMap-Contributors

node	position		id	[...]	type	[...]	6 custom property keys and values		
	x	y					${}^1k_1, {}^1V_1$...	${}^6k_1, {}^6V_1$
1	x_1	y_1	id_1	reserved for handlers	t_1	reserved for handlers	${}^1k_1, {}^1V_1$...	${}^6k_1, {}^6V_1$
2	x_2	y_2	id_2		t_2		${}^1k_2, {}^1V_2$...	${}^6k_2, {}^6V_2$
3	x_3	y_3	id_3		t_3		${}^1k_3, {}^1V_3$...	${}^6k_3, {}^6V_3$
	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots		\vdots		\vdots	\ddots	\vdots
n	x_n	y_n	id_n		t_n		${}^1k_n, {}^1V_n$...	${}^6k_n, {}^6V_n$
	2 x float		string	float	string	float	2 x string	...	2 x string

Figure 3: Data structure of edge (left) and node (right) description arrays E and O

Figure 2 shows eNetEditor's user interface for the creation of nodes and edges with arbitrary property keys and property values. The output in the specified XML-format, as required by SUMO's netconvert.exe, is exemplified in Listing 1 and Listing 2. The corresponding node and edge xml-files are created by parsing the described data structures and can be initiated by a keyboard entry of the buttons o and e respectively.

Listing 1: Example edge definition file in the SUMO specified xml-format (typically .edg.xml)

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<edges>
  <edge from="1" id="1to5" intensityProfile="TGw3West" numLanes="1" numVeh="1050"
    priority="4" speed="8.333" to="5"/>
  <edge from="1" id="1to11" intensityProfile="TGw3West" numLanes="1" numVeh="1050"
    priority="4" speed="8.333" to="11"/>
  <edge from="1" id="1to13" intensityProfile="TGw1West" numLanes="2" numVeh="14900"
    priority="9" speed="13.889" to="13"/>
  ...
</edges>
```

Listing 2: Example node definition file in the SUMO specified xml-format (typically .nod.xml)

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<nodes>
  <node id="1" type="priority" x="1106.15" y="339.02" z="0"/>
  <node id="2" type="traffic_light" x="1074.55" y="419.47" z="0"/>
  <node id="3" type="priority" x="1221.08" y="485.55" z="0"/>
  <node id="4" type="right_before_left" x="1347.50" y="443.89" z="0"/>
  ...
</nodes>
```

3.1.2 Connections

Every edge in SUMO represents a road, on which vehicles can travel into one direction. A bidirectional street in SUMO would therefore be modeled by two edges. Each edge further consists of one or more lanes. Most nodes in a network have at least one incoming and one outgoing lane. When generating a network, netconvert will make assumptions about these connections. However, many complex junctions' structure will deviate from the assumptions made by netconvert's generalized heuristics. Figure 4 shows such an irregular junction with many specific lane-to-lane (red) connections. To allow these kinds of

Figure 4: A complex junction structure in SUMO with irregular connections

junction definitions and for their correct representation and functionality, connections between nodes' (junctions)' incoming and outgoing lanes often need to be specified explicitly.

These connections can be specified in SUMO by explicitly declaring them in a separate connection file in xml format, typically .con.xml. Since connections are lane-specific definitions, each connection possesses 6 degrees of freedom: the incoming lane's parameters, specified by (1) its origin and (2) destination node and (3) its lane index and the outgoing lane's parameters, specified by (4) its origin and (5) destination node and (6) its lane index. The incoming edge's destination and the outgoing edge's origin node, parameters (2) and (4) will most often be identical.

Figure 5: Connection input dialog

The chosen data format for the connection specification is a 3-dimensional array C , where each element $c_{i,j,k}$ represents an incoming lane and contains a list of connections to outgoing lanes. The connection variable C has the following structure:

$$C^{n \times n \times l} = (c_{i,j,k}), \text{ with ...} \quad (3)$$

incoming lane's origin node index $i = 1 \dots n$,
incoming lane's destination node index $j = 1 \dots n$,
incoming lane's index $k = 1 \dots l$,
number of nodes n and
lane number of the edge with the most lanes l .

Whereas the indices i, j , and k of each element in $(c_{i,j,k})$ represent an origin lane, each element $c_{i,j,k}$ itself is a list of connecting destination lanes:

$$c_{i,j,k} = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 & s_1 & t_1 \\ r_2 & s_2 & t_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ r_x & s_x & t_x \end{bmatrix}, \text{ with ...} \quad (4)$$

outgoing lane's origin node index $r = 1 \dots n$,
outgoing lane's destination node index $s = 1 \dots n$,
outgoing lane's index $t = 1 \dots l$,
number of nodes n ,
lane number of the edge with the most lanes l and
number of incoming lane's connections x .

Connections will be guessed by netconvert if incoming and outgoing edges exist and no lane connections are specified for a node. Connections can also be specified in eNetEditor using the dialog box shown in Figure 5, which can be called by the keyboard entry of the button **c**. The resulting xml file (typically .con.xml) is automatically generated after closing the dialog window. The example of a resulting xml is shown in Listing 3.

Listing 3: Example connection definition file in xml-format (typically .con.xml)

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<connections>
  <connection from="110to105" fromLane="0" to="105to66" toLane="0"/>
  <connection from="110to105" fromLane="1" to="105to66" toLane="1"/>
  <connection from="110to105" fromLane="2" to="105to124" toLane="0"/>
  ...
</connections>
```

3.1.3 Lanes

Next to connections, lanes can be attributed with further specifications that serve two purposes: visualization and lane-based restrictions or allowances. eNetEditor allows the specification of these introduced parameters by calling the dialog window (shown in Figure 6) with the keyboard entry of button r . The corresponding variable R consists of a list implemented as a 2-dimensional array

Figure 6: Lane-based specifications input dialog

$$R=(r_i) \text{ with ...} \quad (5)$$

lane specification i r_i ,

lane specification index $i = 1 \dots r_{ln}$ and

total number of lane specifications ln ,

where element r_i contains all lane-based parameters for the corresponding lane:

$$r_i = [{}^Lid_i \quad a_i \quad d_i \quad s_i \quad w_i], \text{ with ...} \quad (6)$$

identifier of lane l_i Lid_i ,

allowed vehicle classes on lane l_i a_i ,

disallowed vehicle classes on lane l_i d_i ,

speed limit on lane l_i s_i (in m/s) and

width of lane l_i w_i (in m).

The parameters *allow* and *disallow* refer to the abstract vehicle parameter *vehicle class*. For the intended functionality, vehicles need to be assigned the corresponding *vehicles class* parameter, as outlined later in section 3.2.

If specified, lane-based specifications require a subsequent generation of the edge descriptions. Further notes regarding on the order of generating individual components of the network can be found later in subsection 3.1.7. An example output is shown in Listing 4 that contains lane-based specifications in the edge definition file (typically .edg.xml).

Listing 4: Example edge definition with lane-specific parameters in xml-format (typically .edg.xml)

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<edges>
...
<edge from="2" id="2to17" numLanes="2" numVeh="17050" priority="9" speed="13.889"
to="17"/>
<edge from="2" id="2to19" numLanes="2" numVeh="18600" priority="9" speed="13.889"
to="19">
  <lane allow="bus, taxi" index="0" width="4"/>
</edge>
<edge from="3" id="3to5" numLanes="1" numVeh="975" priority="4" speed="8.333"
to="5"/>
...
</edges>
```

3.1.4 Bus stops

To model public transport behavior, recurring vehicle halts can be specified in SUMO using *bus stop* objects. eNetEditor allows the definition of bus stops using an input dialog that can be called by the keyboard entry b and is shown in Figure 7. The corresponding variable B consists of a list, implemented as a 2-dimensional array

Figure 7: Bus stop input dialog

$$B=(b_i), \text{ with ...} \quad (7)$$

specification of bus stop i b_i ,

bus stop index $i = 1 \dots b_{st}$ and
total number of specified bus stops b_{st} ,
where each element b_i contains all parameters for the corresponding bus stop

$$b_i = [{}^B id_i \quad l_i \quad {}^B j \quad {}^B x_{s,i} \quad {}^B x_{e,i}] , \text{ with ...} \quad (8)$$

identifier of bus stop b_i ${}^B id_i$,
lane on which bus stop b_i is located l_i ,
index of bus stop b_i on lane l_i ${}^B j = 1 \dots 26$,
start position of bus stop b_i on lane l_i ${}^B x_{s,i}$ (in m) and
end position of bus stop b_i on lane l_i ${}^B x_{e,i}$ (in m).

The output is a SUMO compatible xml-file, which is exemplified in Listing 5.

Listing 5: Example bus stop definition file in the SUMO specified xml-format

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<additional>
  <busStop id="bS_2to19_0a" lane="2to19_0" startPos="10" endPos="25"/>
  <busStop id="bS_54to72_0a" lane="54to72_0" startPos="10" endPos="25"/>
  <busStop id="bS_54to72_0b" lane="54to72_0" startPos="35" endPos="50"/>
  ...
</additional>
```

3.1.5 Charging stations

Charging stations constitute the infrastructural complement to the energy consumption of vehicles. In analogy to bus stops, eNetEditor also allows the definition of charging stations, where compatible vehicles can be supplied with a specified power, if operational conditions allow. The placement and definition of bus stops in the network is similar to that of bus stops. The dialog for the definition of charging stations can be called in eNetEditor by the keyboard entry t . eNetEditor's dialog window is shown in Figure 8. Variable T contains all of the network's charging station information in form of a list, implemented as a 2-dimensional array

$$T=(t_i), \text{ with ...} \quad (9)$$

specification of charging station i t_i ,
charging station index $i = 1 \dots t_{cs}$ and
total number of specified charging stations t_{cs} ,

Each element t_i contains all parameters for the corresponding charging station:

$$t_i = [{}^T id_i \quad l_i \quad {}^T j \quad {}^T x_{s,i} \quad {}^T x_{e,i} \quad {}^T P_i \quad {}^T \eta_i \quad T_i \quad d_i \quad c_i] , \text{ with ...} \quad (10)$$

identifier of charging station t_i ${}^T id_i$,
lane on which charging station t_i is located l_i ,
index of charging station t_i on lane l_i ${}^T j = 1 \dots 26$,
start position of charging station t_i on lane l_i ${}^T x_{s,i}$ (in m),
end position of charging station t_i on lane l_i ${}^T x_{e,i}$ (in m),
charging power of charging station t_i ${}^T P_i$ (in W),
charging efficiency of charging station t_i ${}^T \eta_i$,
delay between arrival and charging at charging station t_i T_i (in s),
(dynamic) charging of moving vehicles above charging station t_i d_i and
compatible vehicle eType(s) that charging station t_i can charge c_i

Figure 8: Charging station input dialog

node	link index	link from	link to
'41'	[1]	'43to41_0'	'41to56_0'
'41'	[2]	'43to41_1'	'41to56_1'
'41'	[3]	'43to41_2'	'41to40_0'
'41'	[4]	'40to41_0'	'41to43_0'
'41'	[5]	'40to41_1'	'41to43_1'
'41'	[6]	'40to41_2'	'41to56_0'
'41'	[7]	'40to41_1'	'41to56_1'
'41'	[8]	'56to41_0'	'41to40_0'
'41'	[9]	'56to41_1'	'41to43_0'
'41'	[10]	'56to41_2'	'41to43_1'

Figure 9: Layout of traffic light signal controlled junction '41' and output of its link indices for its program definition

The output is an xml-file that is compatible with SUMO and the implementations described in [6] for modeling the energy consumption of vehicles and their energy supply with the specified infrastructure elements. An output is exemplified in Listing 6.

Listing 6: Example charging station definition file in xml-format

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<additional>
  <chargingStation id="cS_2to19_0a" lane="2to19_0" startPos="10" endPos="25"
    chrgpower="200000" efficiency="0.95" chargeDelay="2" chargeInTransit="0"
    eType="a"/>
  <chargingStation id="cS_17to2_0a" lane="17to2_0" startPos="0" endPos="62"
    chrgpower="220000" efficiency="0.9" chargeDelay="5" chargeInTransit="1"
    eType="b"/>
  <chargingStation id="cS_17to2_1a" lane="17to2_1" startPos="0" endPos="62"
    chrgpower="250000" efficiency="0.9" chargeDelay="5" chargeInTransit="1"
    eType="a"/>
  ...
</additional>
```

3.1.6 Light signal systems

The definition of traffic light signal system plans for nodes of type *traffic_light* takes place during the network creation by netconvert. In most cases, the automatically generated programs/plans of a junction's light signal system will deviate from its real behavior. SUMO allows multiple ways to interact with light signal systems, both during simulation definition and during runtime. Whereas traffic light signals systems can be declared as actuated for vehicle-flow based triggering or their program switched during simulation runtime using TraCI [9] or WAUT [10], it is also possible to declare static programs with phases of constant durations. Junction's programs can often be sufficiently approximated by a static program, if the period under observation is characterized by similar traffic intensities.

Each phase of a traffic light-signal system in SUMO consists of a duration and a state, where the state is an aggregation of all connection/link states. While the indexing of links is (currently)

Figure 10: Sequence chart of the network creation process

carried out in clockwise order, one difficulty of defining programs beforehand is that link indices are defined by netconvert and are known only after a junction polygon within the net file has been created. Therefore, the chosen solution for eNetEditor is the manual definition of traffic light signal programs in the network file (.net.xml). After the network generation, however, eNetEditor parses the generated network file for all junctions controlled by a traffic light signal system and their link indices and outputs these to support the user with the definition of light signal programs. Figure 9 exemplifies a traffic light signal controlled junction ('41') along with its corresponding output.

3.1.7 Network creation

After all constituents of the simulation's road network have been specified in eNetEditor's graphical user interface and user dialogs, the network can be created with the specified parameters using the sequence chart shown in Figure 10.

It is a multi-stage creation process that ultimately results in a call to netconvert, passing it all required files, to generate the net file (.net.xml). Bus stop and charging station definitions are created separately (in .add.bStop.xml and .add.chrg.xml respectively) as *additional files* and can subsequently be used under the xml tag <additional> of a SUMO configuration. The generated command line that executes netconvert with the required arguments has the following syntax:

```
netconvert.exe -n genNets\Test.nod.xml -e genNets\Test.edg.xml -o genNets\Test.net.xml -x
genNets\Test.con.xml.
```

3.2 Vehicle definitions and generation

The creation of a scenario by filling a defined network with life, i.e. vehicle objects with routes, initially requires defined vehicle types. SUMO allows the definition of various vehicle types along with their parameters that vehicle objects have access to. Most of these parameters are used by implemented vehicle models and include physical constraints and descriptions of the vehicle itself (e.g. maximum speed, vehicle length, color), driver specific parameters (e.g. minimum gap between vehicles, impatience, deviation from speed limit) or model specifications (e.g. the car following behavior, lane-change model, and other user-defined devices. Based on previous implementations described in [6], an energy device has been implemented in SUMO that allows the realistic recreation of the energy variation of vehicles' energy content during simulation runtime, based on newly introduced and defined vehicle parameters, such as vehicle mass, maximum battery capacity (i.e. energy content), drivetrain efficiencies, or various drag coefficients. To attract a wide user base, the goal of these implementations was simplicity by introducing basic physical and comprehensible vehicle parameters. After defining vehicle types, vehicle objects can be instantiated with *vehicle attributes* (initial values) for different model variables. These parameters are contained within each vehicle object itself, are not part of the vehicle type definition and therefore need to be set separately, e.g. manually or by a router described in 3.3. Most popular among these parameters are the vehicle's initial speed, its desired lane to depart from (enter the simulation), its departure (simulation entry) time, or its route. Figure 12 shows the class diagram of the vehicle attribute structure as definable in eNetEditor. The newly introduced energy device and its

Figure 11: Vehicle type input dialog

Figure 12: Structure of vehicle and vehicle type attributes as implemented in eNetEditor, represented in form of a UML class diagram

attributes are shown in green as well as the initial value of a vehicle object's energy content.

The configuration of vehicle attributes can be performed manually. However, in large simulation scenarios this task is carried out by the different routers during traffic demand generation and calibration that will be described in section 3.3. In the following, an overview will be given on eNetEditor's data structures and user interface in for definition and generation of vehicle types.

Vehicle types can be specified with all relevant parameters in eNetEditor using the user interface shown in Figure 11. Vehicle type properties are stored in the 2-dimensional array V of the following structure

$$V^{n_v \times 27} = (v_i), \text{ with ...} \quad (11)$$

vehicle type index $i = 1 \dots n_v$ and

total number of vehicle type definitions n_v .

In the same list-type format as introduced in section 3.1 for lanes, bus stops, and charging stations, each vehicle type description v_i contains 28 parameters that are exemplified in Listing 7. It also shows the xml format required by SUMO and the implemented energy device [6] for the correct definition of vehicle types.

Listing 7: Example vehicle type definition file in the SUMO specified xml-format with additional parameters used by the newly implemented energy device [6]

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<vType id="car" accel="2" decel="5" maxSpeed="42" length="4.5" minGap="2.5" sigma="0.5"
  speedDev="0.05" speedFactor="1.1" tau="1" impatience="0.1">
  <param key="MaxBatKap" value="20000"/>
  <param key="PowerMax" value="80000"/>
  <param key="Mass" value="2000"/>
  <param key="InternalMomentOfInertia" value="50"/>
  <param key="FrontSurfaceArea" value="2.0"/>
  <param key="AirDragCoefficient" value="0.4"/>
  <param key="RadialDragCoefficient" value="0"/>
  <param key="RollDragCoefficient" value="0.15"/>
  <param key="ConstantPowerIntake" value="40"/>
</vType>
```

```

<param key="PropulsionEfficiency" value="0.8"/>
<param key="RecuperationEfficiency" value="0.5"/>
<param key="eType" value="a"/>
</vType>

```

If left unspecified, default values are assigned to the vehicle energy model parameters, which are explained in more detail in [6].

3.3 Traffic demand generation and calibration

After the definition of the network and declaration of vehicle types, the target traffic scenario can be finalized by a subsequent traffic demand generation and, if desired, its calibration. Initial and most important part of vehicle instantiation is the definition of vehicle routes. For this purpose, SUMO comes with a variety of routers. Secondly, initial parameters of the routed vehicle objects need to be set. SUMO's mostly applied routers for the creation of traffic demand are

- MAROUTER:** macroscopic data from origin/destination-matrices and traffic assignment zones or districts is used to assign routes to vehicles within a given network,
- DFROUTER:** detected vehicle flow data is used to calculate the flow proportion at junctions to build vehicle routes [11], and
- JTRROUTER:** definitions of traffic flows on edges and turn ratios at junctions are used to compute vehicle routes within a given network.

For the creation of traffic scenarios using MAROUTER, *SUMO Traffic Modeler* has been developed [12], which is a very convenient and functional third-party tool that supports the generation traffic demand within an existing network. It aims at supplementing a network with demographic data to create time-varying origin/destination-data, which can be used by SUMO's MAROUTER for the generation of vehicle routes. Therefore, eNetEditor focuses on utilizing SUMO's JTRROUTER and (more importantly) DFROUTER for the rapid generation of traffic demand, which is described in more detail in section 3.3.1.

After an initial set of desired routes (edge-by-edge declarations) or trips (origin-destination declarations) has been generated by a router that most often does not take into account the resulting interaction between vehicles, the route choices for individual vehicles need to be calibrated to create realistic traffic scenarios by distributing vehicles iteratively among alternative routes within the network. Two of the most widely utilized applications for traffic calibration are

Figure 13: Class diagram of traffic demand generation and calibration structure in SUMO and eNetEditor

DUAROUTER: based on [13], this user assignment algorithm aims at finding a dynamic user equilibrium for given vehicle trips by assigning routes iteratively until no vehicle can reduce its travel time by an alternative route choice and

cadyts: based on [14], this method further takes into account a supply model of the network to iteratively find a stationary condition, which is consistent with existing traffic counts.

Figure 13 shows the implemented data structure for generating and calibrating traffic demand that the following sections will give more details on. The necessary steps in eNetEditor will further be outlined to build calibrated traffic scenarios. The components shown in red are not implemented in eNetEditor. For creating routes based on existing origin/destination matrices with MAROUTER, the application of *SUMO Traffic Generator* is recommended instead.

3.3.1 Traffic demand generation

For the generation of vehicle instances and routes, eNetEditor offers two possibilities: JTRROUTER and DFROUTER.

3.3.1.1 JTRROUTER

For demand generation with JTRROUTER, eNetEditor allows the definition of vehicle flows and junction turn ratios.

Flow definitions are stored in the 2-dimensional array F with the following structure:

$$F^{n \times 8} = (f_{i,k}), \text{ with ...} \quad (12)$$

flow index $i = 1 \dots n$,
property index $k = 1 \dots 8$ and
total number of flow definitions n .

Each element f_i contains all required parameters of a flow definition:

$$f_i = [{}^F id_i \quad {}^F t_{s,i} \quad {}^F t_{e,i} \quad {}^F e_i \quad {}^F V_i \quad {}^F T_i \quad {}^F l_i \quad {}^F v_i], \text{ with ...} \quad (13)$$

identifier of flow definition f_i ${}^F id_i$,
start time of flow definition f_i ${}^F t_{s,i}$,
end time of flow definition f_i ${}^F t_{e,i}$,
origin edge of flow definition f_i ${}^F e_i$,
number of vehicles in flow definition f_i ${}^F V_i$,
vehicle type of flow definition f_i ${}^F T_i$,
departure (initial) lane of flow definition f_i 's vehicles ${}^F l_i$ and
departure (initial) speed of flow definition f_i 's vehicles ${}^F v_i$.

The resulting xml-output is shown in Listing 8.

Listing 8: Example vehicle flow definition file in the SUMO specified xml-format

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<flows>
  <flow id="86to11flow1" begin="0" end="8640" from="86to11" number="88" type="car"
    departLane="random" departSpeed="random"/>
  <flow id="87to13flow1" begin="0" end="8640" from="87to13" number="90" type="car"
    departLane="random" departSpeed="random"/>
  <flow id="88to13flow2" begin="0" end="8640" from="88to13" number="15" type="bus"
    departLane="random" departSpeed="random"/>
  ...
</flows>
```

The typical use-case of JTRROUTER is that incoming flows into a network are defined at the network boundaries, along with turn ratio definitions at junctions to fill the network with vehicle interaction. When the vehicle flow input dialog is opened for the first time, one vehicle flow is initialized for each incoming edge into the regarded network, whose parameters have to be specified. An edge $e_{i,j,1}$ is identified as an incoming edge if its origin node is not a destination node of any other edge (not even $e_{j,i,1}$). Equation 14 formally defines the set of incoming edges E_I as

$$E_I = \{e_{i,j,1} | \forall j \in [0, n]: e_{i,j,1} = 0\}. \quad (14)$$

In addition to vehicle flows, turning ratios need to be defined at junctions to feed JTRROUTER with all required information. The concept behind the structure for the turn ratio definitions at junctions is similar to that of connections described in section 3.1.2. The main difference between the two declarations is that connections are lane-based definitions (each connection is described by an incoming and outgoing *lane*), where turning ratios are edge based (each turn ratio is described by an incoming and outgoing *edge*). Consequently, the complexity for turn ratio definitions at junctions is lower than that of connections and can be reduced to three degrees of freedom: the incoming and outgoing edge, each described by their origin and destination nodes, where the destination node of the incoming edge is identical to the origin node of the outgoing edge. Each resulting turn ratio is a sequence of three nodes, attributed with a probability. The chosen data structure for turn ratio definitions is a three-dimensional matrix, implemented as

$$J^{n \times n \times n} = (j_{k,l,m}), \text{ with ...} \quad (15)$$

- origin node index of incoming edge $k = 1 \dots n,$
- destination/origin node index of incoming/outgoing edge $l = 1 \dots n,$
- destination node index of outgoing edge $m = 1 \dots n,$
- total number of nodes n and
- turn ratio (probability) $j_{k,l,m} = [0,1].$

Even if J grows exponentially with the amount of nodes, the resulting variable will most often be a sparse matrix, whose required amount of memory can correspondingly be reduced by explicitly declaring it as one in MATLAB (command: *sparse*). Since junction turn ratio definitions are treated as probabilities when JTRROUTER creates vehicle routes, the definitions have to meet requirements to be valid. For the conservation of vehicle flows at junctions, equation 16 defines that the turning ratios from an incoming edge, taken from the adjacency matrix $E=(e)$, must add up to 1. The resulting variable J is automatically validated accordingly when entering turning ratios. Listing 9 exemplifies the xml-output for the definition of junction turn ratios.

$$\sum_m j_{k,l,m} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } e_{k,l,1} \neq 0 \\ 0 & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Listing 9: Example junction turn ratio definition file in the SUMO specified xml-format

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<turns>
  <fromEdge id="23to29">
    <toEdge id="29to30" probability="0.2"/>
    <toEdge id="29to33" probability="0.3"/>
    <toEdge id="29to34" probability="0.5"/>
  </fromEdge>
  ...
</turns>
```


Figure 14: Input dialog for vehicle flow definitions

The vehicle flow and junction turn ratio input dialogs are shown in Figure 14 and Figure 15 and can be called by the keyboard entries of **f** and **c** respectively (due to their similarity, junction turn ratios can be defined along with connections in the lower half of the same input window as shown in Figure 5).

Figure 15: Input dialog for junction turn ratio definitions

If the vehicle flow and junction turn ratio definitions have been created, the specified scenario can be built with a keyboard entry **j**. This

(1) calls JTRROUTER with all required options, which returns vehicle routes that (2) are used to build the resulting SUMO configuration (scenario) file, which is saved in the working directory. The following syntax exemplifies the created command line call to of JTRROUTER with all required options:

```
jtrrouter --random 1 -f Test.flows.xml -t Test.turns.xml -n Test.net.xml -o Test.rou.xml.
```

3.3.1.2 DFROUTER

If the regarded road network is equipped with induction loops or other sensors to measure vehicle traverses, the measurement data can be used to build vehicle routes using DFROUTER, which performs a stochastic route estimation for vehicles. eNetEditor offers an interface to DFROUTER that will be described in this section.

For the definition of induction loops (detectors), the keyword *numVehs* has been reserved as a property name for edges described in section 3.1.1. If vehicle counts exist for an edge, their values can be assigned to the edge attribute *numVehs* for subsequent processing to build a command line argument for DFROUTER, including detector and vehicle count definitions. DFROUTER declares routes for two vehicle types: *PKW* and *LKW*, representing the average passenger and commercial/freight vehicle in the simulation scenario respectively. *PKW* and *LKW* need to be declared as vehicle types in eNetEditor before building the scenario using DFROUTER's routes. The following descriptions are further required:

Detector Definitions: Detector definitions are built according to the declaration of the attribute *numVehs* on the corresponding edge, as exemplified in Listing 10 and

Vehicle Counts: Synthetic vehicle counts are generated according to the specified value of the *numVehs* attribute. Their timestamps are distributed according to the daily traffic curve *TGw2West* from [15] (Figure 2-4) within a user-specified time (e.g. 15:00--18:00) and aggregation periods (e.g. 20 minutes). A constant distribution of 95% passenger and 5% commercial/freight vehicles is currently assumed. The vehicle flow measurement file is exemplified in Listing 11.

Listing 10: Example induction loop (detector) definition as input for the DFROUTER command line

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<detectors>
  <detectorDefinition id="det0_1to5_0" lane="1to5_0" pos="0"/>
  <detectorDefinition id="det1_1to11_0" lane="1to11_0" pos="0"/>
  <detectorDefinition id="det2_1to13_0" lane="1to13_0" pos="0"/>
  ...
</detectors>
```

Listing 11: Example of the synthetically generated vehicle flow measurement file for DFROUTER command line

```
Detector;Time;qPKW;vPKW;qLKW;vLKW
det0_1to5_0;0;4.2989;7;0.22626;5
det0_1to5_0;20;8.334;7;0.43863;5
det0_1to5_0;40;10.5241;7;0.5539;5
```

```
det1_1to11_0;0;4.4204;7;0.23265;5
```

...

If all required definitions have been made, the generation of a scenario with vehicle routes from DFROUTER can be initiated by the keyboard entry `d`. Much like the process defined in 3.3.1.1 for JTRROUTER, this (1) calls DFROUTER with all required options. DFROUTER then returns two files: a route file containing a list of all generated routes and a vehicle instantiation file (with reference to the declared routes). These files (2) are subsequently used to build the resulting SUMO configuration. The following command exemplifies the DFROUTER execution to build the described routes:

```
dfrouter --random 1 --net-file Test.net.xml --detector-files Test.det.xml --measure-files
Test.flowMeas.xml --routes-output Test.rou.xml --emitters-output Test.veh.xml --time-step 1200
--departlane random --departspeed random --vtype true
```

The sequence chart for traffic demand generation with is shown in Figure 16.

3.3.2 Traffic demand calibration

The problem of the routers described in section 3.3.1 is that vehicle instances are assigned a route under static conditions, e.g. by searching for the shortest path through the network. Prevailing traffic conditions are not regarded. This task can be compared to that of trying to find the shortest way through a traffic-intense urban area, only using a map, in hope that the chosen route will be the fastest or the one with the least amount of energy required. It is obvious that prevailing traffic conditions can have a high impact on these optimization criteria. In real traffic, participants without (also often with) assistance usually need a few tries, where iterative variations of departure time and route choice ultimately yields the optimal perceived route for a recurring trip.

A variety of methods exist for traffic simulations that aim to minimize a cost function to find an optimum route distribution among participants (vehicles) in a similar manner as described above. In the scope of eNetEditor, demand calibration refers to the adaption of route assignments. A comparison between different traffic demand assignment methods can be found in [16]. eNetEditors provides an interface to two established implementations for SUMO that aim to optimize the route assignment for vehicle instances: DUAROUTER and cadyts. The basis for both is a validated set of vehicle trips, each consisting of origin, destination, and departure time. These parameters are taken from the route definitions that were stochastically determined by

Figure 16: Sequence chart of the traffic demand creation process using JTRROUTER and/or DFROUTER

DFROUTER. The calibration of traffic demand in eNetEditor is implemented as a 2-phase process:

DUAROUTER: Vehicle routes are distributed by creating alternative routes and evaluating the resulting edge-based weights for specified vehicle trips, until no vehicle can modify its route choice without increasing its travel cost. One of the outputs is a vehicle route file for vehicles containing alternative route probabilities and corresponding travel costs.

cadyts: cadyts itself performs no routing. The alternative routes created by DUAROUTER are evaluated and vehicle route choices adapted, such that the chosen routes comply with detector measurements passed as an input to cadyts.

If traffic scenarios are to be calibrated with cadyts, a previous calibration with DUAROUTER is required in eNetEditor to obtain a required alternative route definition for cadyts.

3.3.2.1 DUAROUTER

While DUAROUTER itself has been implemented in C++, the iterative process of finding alternative routes and executing the simulation has been implemented in form of a Python script, `dualterate.py`. eNetEditor automates the creation and execution of the required command-line argument by the keyboard entry of the **u**, if previous vehicle routes from DFROUTER (section 3.3.1.2) are present. These routes are stripped down to each of their trip definitions using the existing Python script `route2trips.py`: the route's origin edge, destination edge, and departure time. A trip definition is exemplified in Listing 12.

Listing 12: Example trip definition as a result of route definitions from DFROUTER used as input for DUAROUTER

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<trips>
  <trip depart="0.00" departLane="random" departPos="0" departSpeed="random"
    from="82to49" id="emitter_det211_82to49_0_0" to="13to16" type="PKW"/>
  <trip depart="0.00" departLane="random" departPos="0" departSpeed="random"
    from="83to33" id="emitter_det212_83to33_0_0" to="10to27" type="LKW"/>
  <trip depart="0.00" departLane="random" departPos="0" departSpeed="random"
    from="84to23" id="emitter_det213_84to23_0_0" to="23to28" type="PKW"/>
  ...
</trips>
```

The resulting output in eNetEditor is a command-line argument that executes the iterative DUAROUTER Python script with the specified options as exemplified in the following command:

```
duaIterate.py -n Test.net.xml -t Test.trips.xml -x detailed -+ "Test.vtypes.xml,
Test.add.chrg.xml,Test.add.bStp.xml" -1 20
```

3.3.2.2 cadyts

If DUAROUTER has finished calibration, a subsequent call to the Python script `cadytsIterate.py` can be made from eNetEditor by keyboard entry of the button **y**. cadyts requires traffic flow measurements in the xml-format exemplified in Listing 13. In regard of the contained information, this measurement file is nearly identical to that required by DFROUTER, with an additional standard deviation for each measurement, only in a different format. Currently, only one percentage value will be queried by eNetEditor, which derives the standard deviation as a fixed percentage of the corresponding flow for all measurement values. The measurement file is constructed from the values of the user-specified edge parameter `numVehs` in the same manner as described in section 3.3.1.2 for DUAROUTER.

Listing 13: Example flow measurement definition created for subsequent call to cadyts

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<measurements>
  <onlink start="0" end="1199" link="1to5" value="4.280" stddev="0.428"
    type="COUNT_VEH"/>
```

```

<onlink start="1200" end="2399" link="1to5" value="8.158" stddev="0.816"
  type="COUNT_VEH"/>
<onlink start="2400" end="3599" link="1to5" value="12.036" stddev="1.204"
  type="COUNT_VEH"/>
<onlink start="0" end="1199" link="1to11" value="4.280" stddev="0.428"
  type="COUNT_VEH"/>
...
</measurements>

```

The resulting output is a command-line argument that executes cadyts with the specified options to iteratively adapt the route choice of vehicles. The following exemplifies a command line call to cadyts with all required input files and arguments:

```

cadytsIterate.py -b 0 -n Test.net.xml -d Test.calibFlowMeas.xml -- "Test.vtypes.xml, Test.add.
chrng.xml, Test.add.bStp.xml" -r Test.rou.alt.xml -W Test.flowsEvaluation.txt -l 20 -a 1200

```

3.3.3 Manual initial vehicle energy content adjustments

Since the current implementation of the described routers are not yet compatible with the newly developed energy device [6], there are currently two possibilities for setting vehicles' initial energy content at their departure (in analogy to the parameters *departSpeed*, *departLane*, etc.): (1) if left unspecified, vehicles' initial energy content is set to *half of the vehicle type's maximum energy content* by default or (2) vehicle instantiations need to be modified manually within the vehicle route file as exemplified by the syntax in Listing 14.

Listing 14: SUMO configuration of a scenario calibrated with cadyts

```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
...
<vehicle depart="0" id="veh1" route="route02" type="ElectricCar" departSpeed="max">
  <param key="ActBatKap" value="1000"/>
</vehicle>
...

```

3.4 User interaction and interface

Beyond the described user dialogs, user interaction is implemented on the basis of hotkeys. eNetEditor can be executed with the following command-line from MATLAB.

```

netBuild('quadraticBackgroundImage.png',widthInMeters,'projectName')

```


Figure 17: eNetEditor's graphical user interface showing a user-specified background image with a user-created network's digraph (left) and a snapshot of the resulting scenario in the SUMO GUI (right)

The first command argument specifies the filename of a quadratic background image for visualization. The second argument specifies the width (= height) in meters as an integer of the regarded network to be modeled. The third argument specifies the project name as a string.

Projets can be saved in the main window at any time with the keyboard entry **s**. If an existing project shall be opened, the above command-line argument must be executed in MATLAB with its project name specified in the third argument. After all windows have finished loading, the project can be loaded with the keyboard entry **l**. An overview of all hotkeys can be found at the bottom of the main window.

4 Example scenario and results

An example scenario was created that represents a section of Braunschweig's road traffic. Traffic measurements were taken from the city's traffic intensity map [17] and used for calibration as described in section 3.3. Figure 17 depicts eNetEditor's user interface along with a created scenario (left) next to its visualization in SUMO's graphical user interface. The SUMO corresponding configuration file, using the vehicle energy device and charging stations, after calibration with cadyts is shown in Listing 15.

Listing 15: SUMO configuration of a scenario calibrated with cadyts

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<configuration ...>
  <input>
    <net-file value="ringSect5.net.xml"/>
    <route-files value="ringSect5_049.cal.xml"/>
    <additional-files value="dua_dump_049.add.xml,ringSect5.DFvtypes.xml,
      ringSect5.add.chrg.xml,ringSect5.add.bStop.xml"/>
  </input>
  <output>
    <battery-output value="iteration_049.battery.out.xml"/>
    <battery-output.precision value="4"/>
    ...
  </output>
  ...
</configuration>
```

The resulting output file (in this case `iteration_049.battery.out.xml`) can be used by subsequent analyses and optimization algorithms (subject of future work) to determine (1) where in the network energy is consumed and (2) which locations are suitable for the placement of charging stations to supply vehicles with adequate energy *on the fly*, i.e. during their operation. Figure 18 shows first results that aim to supplement these future analyses.

Whereas the left image shows the cumulated energy that was consumed by all vehicles in the simulation, the center and right image focus on the energy consumption's complement: the time, which can be used for transferring energy into vehicles. If vehicles can be charged while moving at arbitrary speeds (e.g. catenary/trolley systems), any location within the road network can

Figure 18: Cumulated energy consumed (left) and cumulated vehicle standstill duration T_{st} , with $T_{st} \geq 0$ s (left) and $T_{st} \geq 10$ s (right), of all vehicles in the simulation over their position

potentially be used for transferring energy into vehicles. The resulting cumulated time of all vehicles in the example scenario as a function of vehicle position is shown in the center image ($T_{st} \geq 0$ s). However, most charging stations (e.g. gas stations) require vehicles to be standing still for a certain duration. If only halts can be used for charging that have a minimum duration, the amount of energy that can be charged reduces drastically. The image to the right shows the cumulated duration of vehicles halts, of which each exceeded 10 seconds in the scenario as a function over vehicle position.

5 Summary and outlook

The development of eNetEditor was motivated by the projects *emil* and *InduktivLaden*, both funded by the German Federal Ministry of Transport and digital Infrastructure. An inductive charging infrastructure and a compatible fully electric prototype bus fleet was successfully integrated in Braunschweig's traffic infrastructure and public transport. With the application of Bombardier's inductive charging system PRIMOVE, vehicles can be charged with powers beyond 200 kW. A crucial factor for the reliable operation of vehicles with limited range is the placement of charging stations. In the project *emil* infrastructure placement was optimized on the basis of measured public transport vehicle trajectories [18] using the FMS interface [19] and GPS loggers.

eNetEditor was developed for city and traffic planners to evaluate the application of alternative energy supply systems in *early* idea and concept phases, where such data is not readily available and only general traffic measurements exists. The ultimate goal is to adapt and implement *flow capture* and *flow refueling* optimization algorithms from [20], [21], and [22] to determine optimal charging infrastructure locations and thereby help in initial estimations of installation costs.

Regarding the validity of the created scenario, calibrated vehicle routes will be checked next against the measured public transport vehicle trajectories. Future implementations in eNetEditor itself include the assistance in modelling public transport by the creation of recurring vehicle routes and their integration in calibrated scenarios. For a more realistic integration and application of DFROUTER's and cadyts' functionalities, user-specifiable daily traffic intensity curves as well as lane-based measurement variations and distributions between passenger and commercial/freight vehicles (*PKW* and *LKW*) will be implemented. Regarding the application of the newly developed energy device [6], routers are currently not compatible with the definition of vehicles' initial energy content at their departure (in analogy to *departSpeed*). It is planned to adapt the routers correspondingly or to implement a parser of vehicle route declarations to allow for custom initial vehicle energy content distributions. In the long term, an import function for .net.xml-files is planned as well as the migration to a platform-independent implementation.

References

- [1] statista. Anzahl der Neuzulassungen von Personenkraftwagen in Deutschland im Jahr 2014 nach Marken. <http://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/167008/umfrage/neuzulassungen-von-pkw-nach-marken-in-deutschland/>, (rev. 02. February 2015)
- [2] statista. Anzahl der Neuzulassungen von Elektroautos in Deutschland in den Jahren 2003 bis 2014. <http://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/244000/umfrage/neuzulassungen-von-elektroautos-in-deutschland/>, (rev. 02. February 2015)
- [3] statista. Anzahl der Tankstellen in Deutschland von 1950 bis 2014. <http://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/2621/umfrage/anzahl-der-tankstellen-in-deutschland-zeitreihe/>, (rev. 02. February 2015)
- [4] BDEW: BDEW-Erhebung Elektromobilität: Zuwachs bei öffentlichen Lademöglichkeiten. <https://www.bdew.de/internet.nsf/id/bdew-erhebung-elektromobilitaet-zuwachs-bei-oefentlichen-lademoeglichkeiten-de> (rev. 02. February 2015)

- [5] Krajzewicz, D., Erdmann, J., Behrisch, M., Bieker, L.: Recent Development and Applications of SUMO - Simulation of Urban MOBility. *International Journal on Advances in Systems and Measurements*, 5 (3&4): 128--138 (2012)
- [6] Kurczveil, T., López, P.A., Schnieder, E.: Implementation of an Energy Model and a Charging Infrastructure in SUMO. In: Behrisch, M., Krajzewicz, D., Weber, M. (eds.) *Simulation of Urban Mobility. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 8594 , pp. 33--43. Springer, Heidelberg (2014)
- [7] Schnieder, L., Stein, C. Schielke, A.G., Pfundmayr, M.: Effektives Terminologiemanagement als Grundlage methodischer Entwicklung automatisierungstechnischer Systeme. *at - automatisierungstechnik*, 59 (1): pp. 62--70 (2011)
- [8] Schnieder, L.: Formalisierte Terminologien technischer Systeme und ihrer Zuverlässigkeit. Dissertation, Technische Universität Braunschweig (2010)
- [9] Wegener, A., Piorkowski, M., Raya, M., Hellbrück, H., Fischer, S., Hubaux, J.-P.: TraCI: An Interface for Coupling Road Traffic and Network Simulators. *CNS '08 - 11th Communications and Networking Simulation Symposium*, Ottawa (2008)
- [10] German Aerospace Center. Simulation/Traffic Lights. http://sumo.dlr.de/wiki/Simulation/Traffic_Lights (rev. 30. December 2014)
- [11] Nguyen, T., Fullerton, M., Krajzewicz, D., Mai, S.T.: DFROUTER - Route estimate method based on detector data. *SUMO2014 - Modeling Mobility with Open Data*, Berlin (2014)
- [12] Papaleontiou, L.G.: High-Level Traffic Modelling and Generation. Master Thesis, University of Cyprus, Nikosia (2008)
- [13] Gawron, C.: Simulation-based traffic assignment - computing user equilibria in large street networks. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Köln, Cologne (1998)
- [14] Flötteröd, G., Bierlaire, M., Nagel, K.: Bayesian demand calibration for dynamic traffic simulations. *Transportation Science*, 45(4): pp. 541--561 (2011)
- [15] Forschungsgesellschaft für Straßen- und Verkehrswesen e.V.: Handbuch für die Bemessung von Straßenverkehrsanlagen (HBS). FGSV Verlag GmbH, Cologne (2009)
- [16] Behrisch, M., Krajzewicz, D., Wang Y.-P.: Comparing performance and quality of traffic assignment techniques for microscopic road traffic simulations. *DTA2008 - International Symposium on Dynamic Traffic Assignment*, Leuven (2008)
- [17] WVI GmbH: Verkehrsmengen im Werktagsverkehr Mo - Fr in [Kfz/24h] - Querschnittswerte. Stadt Braunschweig, Braunschweig (2009)
- [18] Kurczveil, T., Schnieder, E.: Messdatenauswertung für die Auslegung einer induktiven Ladeinfrastruktur für den öffentlichen Personennahverkehr in Braunschweig. *AAET 2014*, Braunschweig (2014)
- [19] HDEI/BCEI Working Group: Fleet Management System Standard Description.
- [20] Hodgson, M.J.: A flow capturing location-allocation model. *Geographical Analysis*, 22(3): pp. 270--279 (1990)
- [21] Berman, O., Larson, R.C., Fouska, N.: Optimal location of discretionary service facilities. *Transportation Science*, 26: pp. 201--211 (1992)
- [22] Kuby, M., Lim, S.: The flow-refueling location problem for alternative-fuel vehicle. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, 39(2): pp. 125--145 (2005)